

Validation and Reliability of the Psychological Scale of Trust in Partners in Marriage

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to measure the validity and reliability of the psychological scale of trust in partners in marriage. Trust is a fundamental element in interpersonal relationships that supports the emotional closeness and stability of couples, especially in long-distance relationships. Referring to Rempel's theory (1985), this study explores three main aspects of trust: predictability, dependability, and faith. The developed measuring instrument involved 30 items and was tested on 49 married participants in Kupang, East Nusa Tenggara. The results of the analysis showed that out of 30 items, 20 selected items met the validity criteria with a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.935 in the first round and 0.966 in the second round. These findings indicate that the trust in partners scale can be used as a reliable research instrument to assess trust in marital relationships. This study provides important insights into the dynamics of trust that can help individuals build and maintain healthy relationships.

KEYWORDS: Marriage, Trust in Partner

INTRODUCTION

Trust is a fundamental and complex concept in interpersonal relationships. According to Rempel (1985), trust is defined as the belief or expectation that another person will act in a way that is beneficial or not detrimental. In this context, trust is not just a collection of beliefs, but a process that involves an individual's assessment of the character and intentions of others. Morrow (2010) emphasized that trust is an important element in every relationship because, without trust, it is difficult to build an intimate and happy relationship. Trust is a vital element in maintaining a relationship, especially for couples who are in a long-distance relationship (Winayanti & Widiasavitri, 2016).

In a long-distance relationship, uncertainty about the status and future of the relationship is higher compared to relationships that are not physically separated. Research by Kauffman (2000) shows that trust is an important requirement for the success of a longdistance relationship. Higher uncertainty in a long-distance relationship can reduce trust, which has the potential to damage the relationship. Increased uncertainty often has a negative impact on trust, so maintaining and building trust is vcrucialin this difficult situation. Trust allows individuals to feel comfortable sharing feelings and emotions with the belief that their partner will respect and not take advantage of what they share (Morrow, 2010 in Winayanti & Widiasavitri, 2016).

Rempel (1985) also identified several key aspects of trust in relationships, including predictability, dependability, and faith. Predictability refers to the extent to which one's behavior can be predicted by another. In the context of a relationship, this means that a partner whose behavior is consistent, even though the behavior may be bad or not ideal, still has an element of predictability. This ability to predict a partner's behavior can create a sense of stability and security in the relationship. Although predictability is not always positive, it is important for partners to understand their partner's actions or reactions in certain situations. For example, one may expect their partner to react a certain way to stress or conflict because they have done so in the past. The second aspect, dependability, refers to the belief that the partner is someone who can be relied on in a variety of situations. This involves responsibility and the ability to fulfill promises or expectations. In a relationship, dependability is very important because it creates a sense of trust that the partner can be relied on to face life's challenges or situations that require support. A reliable person provides a sense of security and comfort because the partner knows they will be there when needed. This includes not only physical presence but also emotional and moral support in the relationship. With dependability, the relationship can develop well because both partners trust each other in terms of responsibility and commitment.

The third aspect is faith, which in the context of a relationship refers to a person's belief in their partner and the relationship itself, especially when faced with uncertainty. This involves the ability to take risks in a relationship, such as trusting a partner's promises or making decisions based on potential long-term benefits, despite uncertainty in the future. This belief can involve sacrifices made

for mutual long-term benefits, such as delaying personal gratification for the good of the relationship. Faith also allows a person to remain attached to a relationship in uncertain situations or when the future is not entirely clear, with the hope that the relationship will grow. This is an important foundation for a deep and long-term relationship, where trust and commitment develop even in the midst of uncertainty or difficulty.

In addition to these aspects, there are various factors that influence trust in a relationship. According to Deutsch (2006) in Winayanti & Widiasavitri (2016), an individual's personality predisposition greatly influences their ability to trust others. Each individual has a different predisposition to trust others; individuals with a high predisposition tend to be more open and trusting, while individuals with a low predisposition may be more skeptical and tend to doubt the intentions of others.

Reputation and stereotypes also play an important role in shaping trust. Even if a person does not have direct experience with another person, individual expectations can be formed through information obtained from other sources, such as friends or the media. The reputation of others often forms strong expectations about elements of trust and distrust and influences the individual's approach to relationships. Actual experiences in interacting with partners also contribute to building trust. Many individuals build perceptions of trust based on their experiences, both positive and negative. Over time, either elements of trust or distrust can dominate the relationship, so individuals tend to generalize these experiences and describe them as relationships with high or low levels of trust. An individual's psychological orientation also influences how they build and maintain social relationships. This orientation is influenced by the relationships they form and vice versa. In order for orientation to remain consistent, individuals will seek relationships that are in line with their character and values. Therefore, building trust in others is not easy and depends heavily on the individual's behavior and the other person's ability to be trusted and take risks. Overall, trust is a key element that underlies healthy relationships, especially in the context of long-distance relationships. Understanding the definitions, aspects, and factors that influence trust can help individuals build and maintain trusting relationships, even when faced with significant challenges. Thus, this study aims to explore more deeply the dynamics of trust in interpersonal relationships, especially in the context of long-distance relationships, and its implications for the success of such relationships.

METHOD

Trust in a partner is an individual's belief in the integrity, honesty, and sincerity of a partner, characterized by the expectation that the partner will maintain commitment, be faithful, and act with good intentions in the relationship (Rempel, 1985). In this study, trust in a partner was measured using an instrument that refers to three aspects identified by Rempel, namely: first, predictability, which includes predictable circumstances, with indicators in the form of consistency in daily behavior. Second, dependability, refers to reliable circumstances, with indicators such as providing consistent emotional support and trust in difficult situations. Third, faith, relates to aspects of belief, with indicators such as optimism about the future of the relationship and trust in the partner's commitment. The trial of this measuring instrument involved 10 participants who functioned as expert assessors, with answer choices on content validity items using a Likert scale of 1-4, where scale 1 indicates respondents "strongly disagree" and scale 4 indicates respondents "strongly agree" to measure the frequency of trust felt by individuals towards their partners.

RESULTS

Based on the compilation of the blueprint of the scale of trust in couples in marriage, the researcher compiled 30 items which are the description of the indicators of trust in couples. The blueprint of the scale of trust in couples can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Blueprint of Trust Scale in Partners

No	Aspect	Indicator	Item Numbers		Total
			Favorable	Unfavorable	
1	Predictability	Consistency in daily behavior	1,2,3	4,5,6	6
2	Dependability	Providing consistent emotional support	13,14,15	16,17,18	12
		Trust in difficult situations	19,20,21	22,23,24	
3	Faith	Optimism about the future of the relationship	25,26,27	28,29,30	12
		Trust in partner's commitment	31,32,33	34,35,36	
Total			15	15	30

Table 2. Results of Discrimination Test of Trust Scale Items in Partners

Initial Analysis Round	Number of Items	Number Remaining	of Item Number Dropped	Description
30	1	20	2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,20 dan 24	Index corrected item total correlation bergerak dari - 0,643 hingga 0,915
20	2	20	-	Index corrected item total correlation bergerak dari 0,465 hingga 0,954

Source: SPSS Version 26 Output

Furthermore, the distribution of valid and failed items on the trust scale in couples can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Distribution of Valid and Invalid Items on the Trust in Partner Scale

No	Aspect	Indicator	Number Items	
			Valid	Fall
1	Predictability	Consistency in daily behavior	1	2,3,4,5,6
2	Dependability	Providing consistent emotional support	10,11,12	7,8,9
		Trust in difficult situations	13,13,15,16,17,18	-
3	Faith	Optimism about the future of the relationship	19,21,22,23	20,24
		Trust in partner's commitment	25,26,27,28,29,30	-
Total			20	10

A summary of the reliability test results can be seen in table 4.

Table 4. Results of the Reliability Test of the Trust Scale in Partners

Number of Item Scale	Round Analysis	Number of Valid Items	Number of Failed Items	Reliability
30	1	20	10	0,935
28	2	28	-	0,966

Source: SPSS Version 26 Output

DISCUSSION

Based on Table 1, namely regarding the blueprint of the scale of trust in couples in marriage that has not gone through validity and reliability testing. It can be seen from the five indicators described that each indicator is represented by favorable and unfavorable indicators which are sufficient as a requirement for the implementation of validity and reliability testing. After the blueprint of the scale of trust in couples in marriage was developed, it was then distributed to 49 participants who were married, either as husband or wife, located in Kupang, East Nusa Tenggara. The researcher used 49 participants because it was considered relevant to test the validity of an instrument. After being distributed based on Table 2, the item discrimination power test was carried out by calculating the correlation coefficient between the distribution of item scores and the distribution of the scale scores themselves to produce a total item correlation coefficient. The corrected item correlation total index of at least 0.30 is considered satisfactory. Based on the results of the item discrimination test using the item discrimination index of 0.3, in the first round, there were 10 items that had a total item correlation index value of ≤ 0.3 , namely items 2, 2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,20, and 24. In the second round, all items had a total item correlation index value of ≥ 0.3 , so the total remaining items in the second round were 20 items with item discrimination coefficients ranging from 0.465 to 0.954. The next thing the researcher did was the distribution of valid and failed items on the trust scale in the pair as seen in Table 2. Reliability is an index that shows the extent to which a measuring instrument can be trusted and relied upon.

Reliability is a translation of the word reliability which has the origin of the words rely and ability. Measurements that have high reliability are called reliable measurements. Reliability is expressed by the reliability coefficient ($r_{xx'}$) whose numbers are in the range of 0 to 1.00. The higher the reliability coefficient approaching 1.00, the higher the reliability. While the lower the reliability coefficient approaching 0, the lower the reliability. Reliability in this study will be tested using the Alpha Reliability Coefficient (α) analysis technique. The method used to measure the reliability of the instrument is Cronbach's alpha method with the help of the SPSS 26 for Windows software program as seen in Table 3. The results of the reliability test on the scale of trust in couples using SPSS 26 for Windows with Cronbach's alpha method showed 0.935 in the first round with 30 scale items tested. The second round of analysis with 20 valid items showed a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.966. Thus, the scale of trust in couples in marriage can be used as an instrument of trust in couples in the Rote Tribe, East Nusa Tenggara in the next research stage, namely to obtain data on trust in couples in marriage.

CONCLUSION

This study successfully explored and measured the validity and reliability of the psychological scale of trust in partners in the context of marriage. Trust is a fundamental element that supports emotional closeness and relationship stability, especially in long-distance relationships. Referring to Rempel's theory (1985), this study identified three main aspects of trust: predictability, dependability, and confidence. Predictability includes the ability to predict a partner's behavior based on consistency in their daily actions, which can create a sense of security even though the partner's behavior is not always ideal. Dependability refers to the belief that a partner can be relied on in various situations, both emotionally and physically, creating a sense of comfort and security that is essential to facing challenges in a couple's life. Meanwhile, confidence reflects an individual's trust in their partner's commitment, especially amid uncertainty, which encourages individuals to take risks in relationships and invest in the sustainability of long-term relationships. Through the development of an instrument consisting of 30 items, this study involved 49 married participants in Kupang, East Nusa Tenggara, and the results of the analysis showed that 20 items met the validity criteria with a very high Cronbach's alpha reliability value (0.935 in the first round and 0.966 in the second round). These findings indicate that the scale of trust in partners can be used as a reliable research tool to assess the dynamics of trust in marital relationships, as well as provide important insights into the factors that influence trust. This study also offers practical implications for individuals in building and maintaining healthy relationships, especially in the context of long-distance relationships that are often faced with various challenges.

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